

ORGANIC PESTICIDES. PART III. SYNTHESIS OF AMIDE DERIVATIVES OF FLUOROPHENOXYCARBOXYLIC ACIDS

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A large number of amide derivatives of fluorophenoxy-carboxylic acids have been synthesised as possible biologically active compounds and plant-growth regulators.

Although the role of halogenated amides as pest control chemicals has been studied extensively, very little information is available on the fluoro or mixed fluoro-halogen analogues. Recently Mitchell *et al.* (*J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1959, 7, 118) have reported the synthesis of amide, lactic acid, and terpenoid derivatives of chlorinated phenoxy-carboxylic acids, possessing interesting biological activity including growth-regulating properties. This activity has been attributed both to the presence of an amide group on the side chain of chlorinated phenoxy acids and the position and degree of chlorination on the benzene nucleus. It has been observed that the amides of chlorinated phenoxyacetic acids are more effective in retarding mature fruit abscission than the corresponding acids.

Keeping these observations in view, we have synthesised a large number of amide derivatives of fluorophenoxy-carboxylic acids as potential biologically active compounds. The fluorophenoxy acids have already been prepared by us (Joshi and Bahel, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 365). The *p*-aminobenzoic acid and *p*-aminosalicylic acid derivatives have been obtained by following the method of Mitchell *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

The pesticidal and other biological activities of these compounds will be communicated in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fluorophenoxy Acid Chlorides.—*o*-Fluorophenoxyacetic, *p*-fluorophenoxyacetic and *p*-fluorophenoxypropionic acids were prepared by the method reported earlier (*loc. cit.*). A mixture of the appropriate fluorophenoxy acid (20 g.) and thionyl chloride (50 g.) was refluxed gently for about 3 hours on a steam bath; the excess of thionyl chloride was removed and the acid chlorides were distilled as colorless liquids. The following acid chlorides were obtained.

TABLE I

Acid chloride.	B.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. <i>o</i> -Fluoro-phenoxyacetyl	150-55°/70-75 mm	83.4%	C ₈ H ₆ O ₂ ClF	51.54	50.95	3.73	3.20
2. <i>p</i> -Fluoro-phenoxyacetyl	* 140-45°/70-80	83.2	C ₈ H ₆ O ₂ ClF	51.33	50.95	3.68	3.20
3. <i>p</i> -Fluoro-phenoxypropionyl	170°/150	84.1	C ₉ H ₈ O ₂ ClF	52.85	53.35	3.76	3.90

* Lit. 106-107°/9 mm.

Amide Derivatives of Fluorophenoxy-carboxylic Acids.—A solution of the appropriate amine (2 M) in dry benzene was added dropwise with frequent shaking to a solution of the acid chloride (1 M) in dry benzene. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 to 2 hours over a steam bath, left overnight, and then filtered. The precipitate was washed with a small quantity of warm benzene, which was subsequently mixed with the original benzene extract. The combined extract was washed with 2% sodium carbonate solution, followed by 2% HCl, and finally with water. After removal of the benzene the residual amide was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The

amides obtained are listed below. To confirm further their amide nature, some of the compounds were hydrolysed and the acids obtained were characterised by their melting points and neutralisation equivalents. In all cases, the parent acids were obtained.

TABLE II

Amide.	M.P. or B.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
(1) <i>p</i> -F*	108°	40%	C ₈ H ₈ O ₂ NF	8.25	8.28
(2) <i>N</i> -Ethyl <i>p</i> -F	73°	84	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂ NF	6.81	7.10
(3) <i>N</i> -(Butyl ^m) <i>p</i> -F	39	42	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ NF	5.78	6.16
(4) <i>N</i> -Benzyl <i>p</i> -F	98°	70	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ NF	5.10	5.40
(5) <i>N</i> -Phenyl <i>p</i> -F	96°	56	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ NF	5.66	5.71
(6) <i>N</i> -(<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl) <i>p</i> -F	103°	65	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCIF	4.84	5.00
(7) <i>N</i> -(<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl) <i>p</i> -F	144°	67	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCIF	4.83	5.00
(8) <i>N</i> -(<i>o</i> -Phenetyl) <i>p</i> -F	64°	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ NF	4.91	4.84
(9) <i>N</i> -cycloHexyl <i>p</i> -F	210-205° /80-90 mm	48	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ NF	4.51	5.62
(10) <i>N</i> -(<i>N</i> -Ethylphenyl) <i>p</i> -F	210-205° /100-20 mm	50	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ NF	4.91	5.12
(11) <i>o</i> -F	120°	45	C ₈ H ₈ O ₂ NF	8.29	8.28
(12) <i>N</i> -Ethyl <i>o</i> -F	59°	85	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂ NF	6.74	7.10
(13) <i>N</i> -Benzyl <i>o</i> -F	69°	90	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ NF	5.64	5.40
(14) <i>N</i> -Phenyl <i>o</i> -F	105°	83	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NF	5.68	5.71
(15) <i>N</i> -(<i>o</i> -Bromophenyl) <i>o</i> -F	99°	65	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NBrF	4.20	4.32
(16) <i>N</i> -(<i>m</i> -Bromophenyl) <i>o</i> -F	97	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ NBrF	4.15	4.31
(17) <i>N</i> -(<i>o</i> -Anisyl) <i>o</i> -F	65	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NF	4.91	5.19
(18) <i>N</i> -(<i>o</i> -Tolyl) <i>o</i> -F	107°	88	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NF	5.70	5.77
(19) <i>N</i> -(<i>m</i> -Tolyl) <i>o</i> -F	84°	86	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ NF	5.68	5.40
(20) <i>p</i> -F*	83°	50	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ NF	7.45	7.65
(21) <i>N</i> -Ethyl <i>p</i> -F'	48	92	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ NF	6.59	6.63
(22) <i>N</i> -Benzyl <i>p</i> -F'	62	88	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₂ NF	5.09	5.12
(23) <i>N</i> -Phenyl <i>p</i> -F'	106	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ NF	5.20	5.40
(24) <i>NN</i> -Diethyl <i>p</i> -F'	26	45	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O ₂ NF	6.20	6.51

* F denotes fluorophenoxyacetamide and F', α -(fluorophenoxy)-propionamide.

N-(*p*-Fluorophenoxyacetyl)-*p*-aminosalicylic acid was prepared by the method of Mitchell, *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) by condensing *p*-aminosalicylic acid (2 g.) with *p*-fluorophenoxyacetyl chloride (3 g.), m.p. 130°, yield 1.7 g. (35% of theory). (Found: N, 4.34. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₂O₅NF: N, 4.59%).

N-(*p*-Fluorophenoxypropionyl)-*p*-aminobenzoic acid was prepared by the above method from *p*-aminobenzoic acid (3.5 g.) and *p*-fluorophenoxypropionyl chloride (5 g.), m.p. 78-79°, yield 4 g. (53% of theory). (Found: N, 4.48. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₄O₄NF: N, 4.62%).

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